

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.8 - Scaling up video

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document describes the preparation and production of the scaling up video of ePLANET project.

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1 Introduction

The ePLANET project considers the development of different dissemination material, in views to increase the visibility of the project's outcomes and maximise the engagement of stakeholders and target groups within the project development.

Within this framework, a constitutional video explaining the project approach and expected impact was produced in M10. It has been used be used as key promotional material in the different social media channels of the project, as well as in presentations, conferences and public events.

Now, a set of 3 regional scaling-up videos has been produced.

Following the Grant Agreement, the ePLANET scaling-up videos have been tailored to the pilot regions, so in national language, and the expected delivery date of the deliverables is M24.

Several screenshots of the videos are included within this document. The videos will be available to be downloaded in the website of the project, as well as through the Youtube ePLANET channel by M24.

2 Screenplay of the video

The ePLANET scaling-up videos have been designed as a key material to highlight the added value of using ePLANET platform and governance strategies within the pilot territories, and so attract other local and regional authorities at national level on the adoption of ePLANET outcomes.

In total, 3 scaling-up videos have been produced, each of them tailored to the specific states of pilot regions. In particular:

- Czech Republic (Zlín region pilot)
- Catalonia (Girona region pilot)
- Greece (Crete island pilot)

The 3 videos have a common initial section, combining motion graphics together with a voice-over presentation (in the national language of each pilot region), followed by a tailored section with two short testimonials from the addressed pilot region.

The total length of each video is around 2'20''.

2.1 Common section

The common initial section has the format of a storytelling animated by motion-graphics. The storytelling highlights the added value of collaboration amongst local authorities to improve the capacities, decision-making and investment opportunities related to the deployment of Energy Action plans. The storytelling follows this structure:

- A- Initial statement on the importance of local authorities regarding Energy Transition actions.
- B- Introduction. Description of the current situation of 3 different municipalities, identifying the key issues.
- C- ePLANET solution.
- D- Benefits of ePLANET users.
- E- Call for engagement.

The included narration in the common storytelling section (voice-over text in national languages) is shown in next table:

Table 2-1 - Text structure within the common initial section

Initial statement	<i>Local public administrations play a key and fundamental role in the Energy Transition. Municipalities aim to fight against climate change.</i>
Description of current situation	<p><i>For example, A-ville has a fund to finance energy renovation actions for buildings and aims to promote a citizen energy community. However, it lacks strategies to engage citizens, and technical knowledge to deploy and manage a photovoltaic installation.</i></p> <p><i>B-ville is a reference on citizen mobilisation. It has an energy transition plan, but it lacks the financial and technical resources to deploy it effectively.</i></p> <p><i>C-ville is a reference in the implementation of renewable energies, but its citizens are not aware of it.</i></p> <p><i>The three municipalities are close to each other, but their Energy Transition is slow due to a lack of coordination and alignment among them.</i></p>
ePLANET solution	<i>ePLANET has developed a digital platform to share energy transition actions, seek support, and work together in coordination.</i>
ePLANET benefits	<p><i>Thanks to ePLANET, cluster collaboration between municipalities becomes possible.</i></p> <p><i>With this new clustering governance, all three municipalities share experiences, resources, and achieve the energy transition more rapidly.</i></p>
Call for action	<p><i>Are you a local administration? Join the ePLANET network and accelerate the energy transition in your municipality!</i></p> <p><i>Contact us and we will help you to improve your Energy Transition!!</i></p>

2.2 Region-tailored section

After the common section, the video continues with a specific region-tailored section, with the format of two testimonials from the specific pilot region, including a project partner and a stakeholder from the selected region.

Recordings from stakeholders diverge from one video to another one, but the message is the same: the recordings try to highlight the benefits the ePLANET tools can provide to end users.

3 Visual aspect

The next images taken from the videos show the overall approach of the graphic design in the video within its different sections.

Figure 3-1 -Video screenshots: initial common section

Figure 3-2 - Video screenshots: regional tailored sections

Figure 3-3 - Video screenshot: final common section and EU disclaimer

4 Online repository

The 3 scaling-up videos have been uploaded in the ePLANET Youtube channel, and will be also accessible via the ePLANET website. The communication and dissemination actions planned for next months will also include the dissemination of those videos through the different channels (LinkedIn, news, twitter, workshops, webinars, etc).

Direct link: www.youtube.com/@ePLANETproject173

